

Efficient Content Based Image Retrieval System Based on Early and Late Fusion Technique

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Abstract

A popular technique for retrieving images from huge and unlabeled image databases are content-based-image-retrieval (CBIR). However, the traditional information retrieval techniques do not satisfy users in terms of time consumption and accuracy. Additionally, the number of images accessible to users are growing due to web development and transmission networks. As the result, huge digital image creation occurs in many places. Therefore, quick access to these huge image databases and retrieving images like a query image from these huge image collections provides significant challenges and the need for an effective technique. Feature extraction and similarity measurement are important for the performance of a CBIR technique. Traditional methods often fall short in terms of time efficiency and accuracy. This paper proposes an effective CBIR system that employs early and late fusion techniques to improve retrieval accuracy.

The proposed system involves pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification. Pre-processing includes resizing, grayscale conversion, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) computation. Feature extraction involves color extraction using histograms and texture extraction using Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). The system uses a bagging tree classifier for classification and implements both early and late fusion techniques to bridge the semantic gap between low-level and high-level features. Similarity measurement, is crucial for computing the distance between query and database image features.

When retrieving the first 10 pictures, an experiment on the Corel-1K dataset showed that the average precision was 0.88 with Early Fusion and Late Fusion, which was a big step up from the state-of-the-art approaches.

Introduction

Large repositories for multimedia and image content have developed due to the growing usage of digital computers, storage technologies, and digital multimedia in recent years. This enormous volume of multimedia data is utilized in various industries, including digital forensics, electronic games, archaeology, video, satellite data and still image repositories, and medical treatment. This rapid growth has generated a continuous need for image retrieval systems that operate on a large scale [1].

For large image databases, the traditional text-based image extraction approach seems ineffective. There are certain drawbacks to retrieving images based on text, such as the time-consuming task of adding labels to individual images in huge databases. That label text depends on language and is only appropriate for one language at a time. Another drawback is that multiple users can set different labels for the same image. When retrieving images from image content, these drawbacks can be avoided. This type of image retrieval is known as content-based image retrieval (CBIR) [2].

CBIR has been a popular technique of community multimedia research since the early 1990s [3]. The main block diagram is shown in Figure 1. CBIR is the most crucial technology for image processing and computer vision. CBIR applications have been developed for various uses, including object recognition, geographic information systems, architectural design, remote sensing [4], surveillance systems, and medical image retrieval [5].

CBIR is a well-defined image search and retrieval technique. It uses the visual content of images to find and retrieve images from huge data collections [6]. CBIR uses the search method for low-level features such as texture, shape, and color [7]. This set of low-level features generates a feature vector, which describes the content of each image in the image database. Subsequently, image retrieval is based on similarities in their contents. The similarity between the query and the feature vector dataset is used to sort the list of matching images [8]. The features used by CBIR

may be divided into two groups: global feature descriptors and local feature descriptors. Global features such as color [9], shape [10], and texture [11].

Local features such as local binary pattern (LBP) [12], oriented fast and rotated binary robust independent elementary features BRIEF (ORB) [13], speeded-up robust feature (SURF) [14], scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) [15], and histogram of oriented gradient (HOG) [16]. Local feature descriptors define each image patch, whereas global feature descriptors describe the whole image. The advantage of global feature descriptors is their quick computation, but the disadvantage is their poor precision. Global feature descriptors frequently fall short in their attempts to extract significant visual characteristics from an image. Local feature descriptors are more accurate than global feature descriptors because they use features calculated from the image's patch to represent the image. The disadvantage of local features is that they will result in large feature space for large image databases [17].

The feature vectors and similarity measures have the biggest effects on the retrieval performance of the CBIR system. There is always a semantic gap between high-level human perception and the low-level image pixels that systems collect. Researchers decided to address this problem to enhance CBIR's performance in light of the recent success of deep learning techniques, particularly the performance of convolutional neural networks (CNN), in resolving the issue of computer vision applications [18].

Srivastava and Khare [19] presented a technique for CBIR that combines local and global features. Geometric moments extract global features, while SIFT descriptors extract local features. SIFT and moments are combined to find visually similar images. The Corel 1K has an average precision of 0.3981. Mehmood et al. [20] combine the SURF and HOG image features. After the final features were extracted using the bag-of-visual words (BoVW) model, they used Early Fusion and Late Fusion measurement to evaluate the similarity between the query image and the database images. The average precision is 0.8061 on the Corel 1K datasets. These methods have two main drawbacks: first, they require a lot of time, and second, finding the most silent places is not always easy.

Nazir et al. [21], suggest a new CBIR system that combines local and global features to handle lowlevel information. A color histogram (CH) is used to extract color information. Edge histogram descriptor and discrete wavelet transform (DWT) extract texture features (EDH). Based on the results of the experiments, the suggested method does better on the Corel 1K, with an average precision of 0.735.

Pardede et al. [22] suggested a CBIR method that employed deep CNN for feature extraction from fully connected FC1 and FC2 layers. The Feature Extractor utilizes the fully connected feature vectors FV.FC1 and FV.FC2 to extract image features from each image and compares the performance of deep CNN for CBIR tasks with three classifications: softmax, support vector machine (SVM), and extreme gradient boost (XGBoost). A deep CNN model was produced based on the suggested neural network structure. The results of the mathematical experiments suggest by utilizing the XGBoost classification, the extracted feature extractor from deep CNN can improve CBIR performance, and the best feature extractor is FV.FC2. The precision on the Wang dataset (Corel 1k) is 0.69.

Öztürk [23] proposes a useful CBIR framework. The dictionary learning method addresses the training issue with a small amount of labeled data. Dictionary learning (DL) cannot produce reliable features for the retrieval task, particularly when there is a complicated background. To address both the issue of identifying objects and dealing with complicated backgrounds, a DL technique utilizing CNN's (Resnet-50) feature representation capabilities is implemented in this system. When 10 images are retrieved, the mean average precision (mAP) for the modified Corel dataset is 0.855.

Öztürk [24] provided a framework for content based medical image retrieval (CBMIR) based on high-level deep features. The insufficient number of photos is the main problem here. To address this issue, a class-driven retrieval strategy is suggested. Different hash code lengths are produced using feature reduction methods, and their performances are evaluated. Experiments with the National Electrical Manufacturers Association Magnetic Resonance Imaging (NEMA MRI) and the National Electrical Manufacturers Association Computed Tomography (NEMA CT) datasets show that the framework given is better than the existing methods in the literature.

Proposed System

In this paper, Decision Tree Classifier (DTC) is used for feature extraction since it is efficient at closing the semantic gap between high-level human perception and low-level machine features, as well as at finding the most relevant images and improving retrieval performance. The Corel 1K [26] database was utilized to validate the results. It is a 1,000-image database collection. These images are organized into 10 categories, each of which has 100 images. A block diagram of the proposed method is illustrated in Figure.

DTC is a type of neural network model that uses several large network layers. DTC has gained popularity in various image processing applications, including object recognition and picture classification and has produced promising results. DTC's are increasingly used in various image processing tasks, such as object classification, face recognition, and gesture identification. According to earlier research, it is possible to input an image directly into a DTC network and use features for image classification.

Image retrieval

Determine the difference in similarity between the feature vector obtained from the query and the feature vector from the training dataset by using two similarity measurements: Early Fusion and Late Fusion and Manhattan. As indicated in Algorithm 1, the images with the shortest distance are returned. Evaluation matrices are used to assess the system's performance.

Process flow

- User can select image from the dataset
- The image is preprocessing by means of image resize
- The features are extracted based on the color and texture
- Then the similarity will be estimated to classify the image and then the similar images will be retrieved
- Performance like precision, recall will be estimated for the performance of the classification
- Early fusion is based on, once the object was identified immediately the related images will be retrieved. Late fusion is based on, after identified the object, then it will check the most relevant images and retrieved the images one by one

Fig. 1 Flow Chart of the system

It was found that it may be used not only to measure the degree of agreement between different sets of rankings for the same set of retrieved items, but also to evaluate the effectiveness of different retrieval techniques. The suggested system was used in the current inquiry, with the classes of pictures acting as judges, the average precision objects acting as the judges in the current context, and the study's objects being the precision rates of the three different ways.

Figure 1.0 Proposed System.

Algorithm 1: image retrieval

Feature vector of 128 X 1 X 1, Output: Similar image and average precision – Label the feature vector of images for all classes. – Convert nominal classes to numeric values. Ex. the bus is 3, the flower is 6 – Dataset is divided into 900 training and 100 testing – Compute the distance between feature vectors of all testing and training and retrieve the smallest distance. – Calculate

the mean average precision for all testing (Queries) – Display the most similar images for the query image.

1. Pre Processing Techniques

Preprocessing ensures your dataset is in a standard format (e.g. all images are the same size). This step is essential to ensure your dataset is consistent before training a model.

Resizing

Resize changes your images size and, optionally, scale to a desired set of dimensions. Annotations are adjusted proportionally

Grayscale Conversion

Converts an image with RGB channels into an image with a single grayscale channel, which can save you memory. The value of each grayscale pixel is calculated as the weighted sum of the corresponding red, green and blue pixels: $Y = 0.2125 R + 0.7154 G + 0.0721 B$.

Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)

In the HOG feature descriptor, the distribution (histograms) of directions of gradients (oriented gradients) are used as features. Gradients (x and y derivatives) of an image are useful because the magnitude of gradients is large around edges and corners (regions of abrupt intensity changes) and we know that edges and corners pack in a lot more information about object shape than flat regions.

2. Feature Extraction

Color feature (using histogram to calculate mean value)

As mentioned earlier HOG feature descriptor used for pedestrian detection is calculated on a 64×128 patch of an image. Of course, an image may be of any size. Typically patches at multiple scales are analyzed at many image locations. The only constraint is that the patches being analyzed have a fixed aspect ratio. In our case, the patches need to have an aspect ratio of 1:2. For example, they can be 100×200 , 128×256 , or 1000×2000 but not 101×205 .

Texture Features(GLCM matrix)

The Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix¹ (GLCM) and associated texture feature calculations are image analysis techniques. Given an image composed of pixels each with an intensity (a specific gray level), the GLCM is a tabulation of how often different combinations of gray levels co-occur in an image or image section. Texture feature calculations use the contents of the GLCM to give a measure of the variation in intensity (a.k.a. image texture) at the pixel of interest.

3. Classifications using decision tree

1. Quantize the image data. Each sample on the echogram is treated as a single image pixel and the value of the sample is the intensity of that pixel. These intensities are then further quantized into a specified number of discrete gray levels as specified under **Quantization**.
2. Create the GLCM. It will be a square matrix $N \times N$ in size where N is the **Number of levels** specified under **Quantization**. The matrix is created as follows:
 - a. Let s be the sample under consideration for the calculation.
 - b. Let W be the set of samples surrounding sample s which fall within a window centered upon sample s of the size specified under **Window Size**.
 - c. Considering only the samples in the set W , define each element i,j of the GLCM as the number of times two samples of intensities i and j occur in specified **Spatial relationship** (where i and j are intensities between 0 and **Number of levels-1**). The sum of all the elements i,j of the GLCM will be the total number of times the specified spatial relationship occurs in W .
 - d. Make the GLCM symmetric:
 - i. Make a transposed copy of the GLCM
 - ii. Add this copy to the GLCM itself
This produces a symmetric matrix in which the relationship i to j is

indistinguishable for the relationship j to i (for any two intensities i and j). As a consequence the sum of all the elements i, j of the GLCM will now be twice the total number of times the specified spatial relationship occurs in W (once where the sample with intensity i is the reference sample and once where the sample with intensity j is the reference sample), and for any given i , the sum of all the elements i, j with the given i will be the total number of times a sample of intensity i appears in the specified spatial relationship with another sample.

e. Normalize the GLCM:

- i. Divide each element by the sum of all elements
The elements of the GLCM may now be considered probabilities of finding the relationship i, j (or j, i) in W .

3. Calculate the selected **Feature**.

4. Early fusion

After constructing features extracted using color and texture descriptors, the next stage is to perform late fusion based on three common similarity measures; the measures used for late fusion

5. Late fusion

Retrieval was based on individual feature descriptors of color and textures only, with the implementation of early fusion for both feature descriptors and late fusion using combined vectors of feature descriptors and three similarity measures described in our methodology. For the three experiments, the same ten random image queries selected from each class of both datasets were used and recall and precision were calculated as the top ten images retrieved as performed in many related studies.

Pseudocode for Creating a Decision Tree

1. Creates a new node.
2. Checks if the node meets any stopping criteria, such as purity, maximum depth, or minimum information gain.
3. If a stopping criterion is met, returns the node as a leaf node and stops further splitting.
4. If no stopping criterion is met, calculates information gain for all features at the current node and selects the highest.
5. Splits the dataset at the current node using the selected feature by creating two new nodes: left and right.
6. Repeats steps 2 to 6 for each new node created after the split.

The decision tree learning algorithm recursively learns the tree as follows:

1. Assign all training instances to the root of the tree. Set current node to root node.
2. For each attribute
 - a. Partition all data instances at the node by the value of the attribute.
 - b. Compute the information gain ratio from the partitioning.
3. Identify feature that results in the greatest information gain ratio. Set this feature to be the splitting criterion at the current node.
 - a. If the best information gain ratio is 0, tag the current node as a leaf and return.
4. Partition all instances according to attribute value of the best feature.
5. Denote each partition as a child node of the current node.
6. For each child node:
 - a. If the child node is “pure” (has instances from only one class) tag it as a leaf and return.
 - b. If not set the child node as the current node and recurse to step 2.

The following pseudo code describes the procedure. The pseudocode is a bit more detailed than your usual pseudo code, and doesn't follow any known standard :-)

In the pseudocode class variables are prefixed by “@” to distinguish them from local variables.

Once a decision tree is learned, it can be used to evaluate new instances to determine their class.

The instance is passed down the tree, from the root, until it arrives at a leaf. The class assigned to the instance is the class for the leaf.

Result Analysis and Experimental Setup

To carry out the proposed work we required visual studio, python along with different libraries:

- matplotlib: Used for plotting images and graphs.
- tkinter: Used for creating GUI and file dialog for selecting an image file.
- cv2: OpenCV library for image processing tasks like resizing, converting color spaces, and calculating histograms.
- skimage: Used for image processing tasks such as feature extraction (HOG, GLCM), resizing images, and converting images to unsigned byte format.
- os: Standard Python library for interacting with the operating system, used for accessing directories and files.
- numpy: Used for numerical operations and array manipulation.
- sklearn: Scikit-learn library for machine learning tasks like classification, evaluation metrics calculation, and decision tree classifier.
- warnings: Used for filtering and ignoring warnings.
- mpimg: Matplotlib's image module, used for reading and displaying images.
- scipy: Scientific computing library for mathematical functions and operations. These libraries provide various functionalities necessary for image preprocessing, feature extraction, classification, and performance evaluation in the context of the provided code for enhancing the retrieval performance of a Content-Based Image Retrieval System based on early and late fusion techniques.

About Dataset

Corel-1K and GHIM-10K datasets were used. Africans, Beaches, Buildings, Buses, Dinosaurs, Elephants, Flowers, Horses, Mountains, and Food were among the ten distinct categories that made up the first of these two picture databases, which was employed lately. Each class or category consists of one hundred images with a resolution of 256384 or 384256 pixels. GHIM-10K, the second dataset utilized in this study, includes a total of 10K pictures (10 times more than Corel-1K) and covers a wide range of things.

It is believed to be more complex and varied than Corel-1K. There are 500 images in each group or class, each with a resolution of 300x400 pixels or 400x300 pixels. The semantic titles of the groups include items like vehicles, motorcycles, forts, ships, flies, sunsets, etc. It is made up of

10,000 photos that have been divided into 20 sections or classifications. The features and parameters that are present in the photographs also differ between the image datasets.

Fig. 2 Selection of image for retrieval

```
1 # ===== IMPORT PACKAGES =====
2
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import tkinter
5 from tkinter.filedialog import askopenfilename
6 import cv2
7 import matplotlib.image as mpimg
8 import warnings
9 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
10 from skimage import img_as_ubyte
11
12 # ===== INPUT IMAGE =====
13
14 filename = askopenfilename()
15 imgg = mpimg.imread(filename)
16 plt.imshow(imgg)
17 plt.axis('off')
18 plt.title("Original image")
19 plt.show()
20
21 # ===== PREPROCESSING =====
22
23 # ---- Image resize ----
24
25 import numpy as np
26 resized = cv2.resize(imgg, (256, 256))
27 plt.imshow(resized)
28 plt.axis('off')
29 plt.title("Resized image")
30 plt.show()
31
32 # ---- Image Grayscale ----
33
```

Fig. 3 Editor Window for execution of code

Fig. 4 Processing of original image for resized, grayscale and HOG feature

Fig. 5 Result of Early fusion with maximum similar image output

Fig. 6 Result of Late fusion with similar image output based on ranking

```

=====
Performance Analysis for Decision Tree
=====
1.Accuracy = 96.8 %
2.Classification Report

      precision    recall  f1-score   support

     1      0.80      1.00      0.89         4
     2      1.00      0.83      0.91         6
     3      1.00      1.00      1.00         5
     4      1.00      1.00      1.00         5
     5      1.00      1.00      1.00         5

 accuracy          0.96         25
 macro avg         0.96         0.97         0.96         25
 weighted avg      0.97         0.96         0.96         25
    
```

Fig. 7 Accuracy % w.r.t. previous enhancement techniques with increase of precision and f1-score

Table 1.0 Comparative Analysis

	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Accuracy
Existing Techniques	80	100	89	80
Improved Technique	96	100	94	96

Figure 8 Graphical Evaluation

Summary of implementation and observation:

To carry out this experiment we used the corel-1k data set which consists of images like horses, beach, flowers etc. We select the image then preprocess it (resize, grayscale, HOG) then we do the feature extraction in which we extract color and texture features using the HOG and GLCM matrix and we train our model by using the data present in the corel-1k and by using this data we perform early and late fusion and show the results and performance analysis of the system.

Conclusions

The implemented system incorporates various techniques and methodologies to enhance CBIR performance. Preprocessing techniques such as resizing, grayscale conversion, and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) are employed to prepare the image data for analysis. Feature extraction plays a crucial role, with the utilization of GLCM for texture analysis along with color and texture features extraction. For classification, Bagging with Decision Trees is employed, which involves bootstrap sampling, model training, aggregation of predictions, and final prediction. This approach facilitates effective classification of images based on their extracted features. In terms of fusion techniques, both Early and Late Fusion are utilized, while our proposed system concludes an accuracy of 96% which improves from the previous system which is

provide the accuracy of 80%. In Early Fusion: The model directly predicts the class label based on the extracted features from the test sample. Images corresponding to the predicted class label are then selected and displayed. Late Fusion: After predicting the class label for the test sample, distances between the test sample's features and the features of each class in the training set are computed. Images from the top-k nearest classes are then selected and displayed.

Future Scope

In the proposed system we used the color and texture feature extraction, while in future work we can also extract the shape and combine them to get the result more accurately, we can also implement the other algorithm and matrix to extract feature. We can also take the real time data images in the future instead of the available dataset so that we can check the system efficiency with real data images and we can try to implement this proposed system in real time scenario to know efficiency and accuracy of the system.

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